

FEATURES OF THE EMERGENCE OF DEVIANT TYPES OF BEHAVIOR

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Abstract: This article provides theoretical information on the types of deviant behavior and the stages of its occurrence. The fact that there is a deviation in the behavior of young people and the change in the direction of the behavior in exceptional cases has been practically studied.

Key words: deviant behavior, social deviation, asocial, delinquent.

Today's world, which is changing at lightning speed, opens up new and great opportunities for humanity and young people, but also exposes them to various dangers that have not been seen before. We are all witnessing how many families and countries face the burden of such threats as religious extremism, terrorism, drug addiction, human trafficking, illegal migration, and "mass culture". Malicious forces are turning the children against their parents and their country, taking their lives. Carelessness and indifference in such a tense and dangerous situation - no matter how hard it is, we have to say openly - this is treason and a crime. Therefore, we, parents, teachers, the public, and the neighborhood should increase our vigilance and awareness in this matter.

Oriental scientists, who consider moral education as the main factor in the development of a person, defined it as "the most important, most honorable, and high-ranking person." Education was measured by the extent to which good and bad habits were formed. Accordingly, any action is described as "right" or "wrong", "good" or "bad". In this understanding, the term "violation" is considered a natural correlate of the norm, that is, a related concept. This concept refers to signs associated with behavior or its symptoms.

The problem of delinquent (against the law, antisocial) morality is the main one for the research of many social sciences. Different approaches are used in relation to illegal ethics. In psychological literature, it is often shown as delinquent morality. The word delinquent means lot, "misdeed, guilt". Under this term, we understand the behavior of a specific person whose morals are contrary to the law and deviate from the laws established in this society and at

this time, endangering other people or social order, peace, and in its last manifestations are criminally punished.

The main types of deviant morality include crime, alcoholism, drug addiction, suicide, adultery, prostitution and mental disorders. Deviance is the result of negative psycho-social development expressed in various forms of loss of moral adaptation and violation of the process of socialization. The first group is a group of representatives of delinquent morals of a person (lat. delinquens, criminal behavior, deed). It includes criminals of the above-mentioned categories, as well as prostitutes and homeless people.

Delinquent behavior is the behavior of a certain person who deviates from the legal norms established in this society and at the same time, endangers the public order. A delinquent person is a subject who exhibits behavior suitable for criminal punishment, possessing sharply deviant morals.

The second group includes representatives of a person's self-destructive morals, that is, through his morals and actions, which lead to faster or slower and irreparable decay of the psyche or the whole organism. These are alcoholics, drug addicts, and suicides.

Finally, the third group consists of non-normative moral representatives of a person, which includes people suffering from various mental disorders.

Deviant behavior can occur in the following stages:

In the first stage, there may be no deviant actions in a "pure" form, but some symptoms may appear: - disobedience, rejection, failure to fulfill certain social requirements (family, school, social group). The reason for this is the wrong educational influence. Social control tries to counteract this effect. Social support should be aimed at: - correction of educational impact (help to teachers, parents); - to a specific person and changing educational activities; If the social diagnosis is successful, it is possible to achieve positive results, otherwise, 2 different results are possible: either the person solves the problems himself, or the deviant behavior is strengthened.

The second stage it is characterized by a deeper violation of social norms, requirements and violations of the primary law (petty thefts, lies, hooliganism). Subgroups include associative behaviors. Manifestations of a person's attitude to social norms: a) a person accepts his behavior as normal and consistent with his values and requirements. b) a person approves of his behavior, believes that it is not only in accordance with his own norms and values, but also in accordance with the norms and values of the group in which he is acting. c) The person evaluates his actions negatively, does not meet his values and requirements.

Timely attention and corrections with the help of diagnosis will give a positive result. Otherwise, there may be deeper disturbances in social behavior.

In the third stage deviant behavior is characterized as follows: repeated acts of breaking the law and gaining social skills in this direction (theft, violence, deeper hooliganism, embezzlement, prostitution, etc.). A person either evaluates his actions as normal and it corresponds to his values and requirements, or he begins an "identity crisis". This crisis leads to social conflicts, which often end with the evaluation of him and society's opinion about him, the identification ideas of the people around him. At this stage, correctional support for negative social views should be intensive and new, socially important ones should be formed.

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According to the decision of the court, on the recommendation of parents, teachers, psychologists, etc., it is possible to issue mandatory sanctions to specialized educational institutions in order to separate them from the harmful effects of the surrounding social environment.

At this stage, there is little hope that the individual will solve problems on their own.

The fourth stage – stable deviant behavior - there is a possibility of acquiring a permanent associative character, which includes repeated and serious illegal actions, dangerous social deviations.

A person may evaluate his behavior negatively, but feel insecure about his ability to overcome it.

The nature and content of correctional measures will remain the same as in the third stage. There is a possibility of successfully solving the problem when social action is avoided, but the general difficulty in getting a positive result is that the "label" (Stigmatization) has already been pressed. Therefore, in unsuccessful support, there is a stable preparation for the initiation of deviant behavior.

The fifth stage – is a stable, high-risk deviant behavior, characterized by persistent associative actions and severe social consequences. A person's attitude to social norms remains the same as at the previous stage. At this stage, the probability of achieving a positive result is low, because the person's separation from society is stable.

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